

MULTISCALE HYBRID COMPOSITES FOR EMI SHIELDING

J. Gnidakoung¹, Y.-B. Park^{1*}, J. W. Keum², H. S. Jeong², Y. B. Jung²

¹ School of Mechanical and Advanced Materials Engineering, UNIST, Ulsan, Korea

² Young Kwang P.M.S., Ulsan, Korea

* Corresponding author (ypark@unist.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Multiscale Hybrid Composites, Carbon Nanomaterials, EMI Shielding*

1 Introduction

Electromagnetic shield can be defined as any means used for the reduction of the electromagnetic field in a prescribed region. The reliability of electronics and communication security needs as well as the rapid growth of radio frequency make the society more demanding in terms of electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding. Concomitantly, environmental issues have driven the production of more and more apparatus and engines, using environmentally friendly energy sources. These devices produce signals that are genotoxic, damaging and altering the DNA in exposed cells of the human body, causing cancer and enhancing cell death rates [1]. Electromagnetic radiation can therefore be a serious health hazard for humans. In electromagnetics, shielding effectiveness (SE) is a concise parameter generally applied to quantify shielding performance and is expressed in decibels (dB).

Carbon fiber composites (CFC) are now playing an important role in avionic and automobile industries, due to their lower densities (1.6-2 g/cm³) than comparable metals (2.5-3 g/cm³) allowing for significant weight savings. Moreover, their particularity stems from their multifunctional potentials; they combine good electrical conductivity and mechanical properties, and are also effective in EMI shielding. Both discontinuous and continuous fibers are used, but continuous fibers are needed to provide high strength and high modulus for structural applications [2]. In terms of continuous fiber applications, woven laminate CFCs are preferred because of their more balanced mechanical properties and their ability to conform to a curved surface without damaging the carbon, making them a good candidate for EMI shielding in industry [3, 4]. This paper investigates EMI shielding efficiency of conductive carbon nanomaterial (CNM) reinforced

woven composites (multiscale composites) within the frequency range of 30-1,500 MHz. Atomized MWCNT sprayed from a pressurized nozzle were deposited as thin coatings on woven carbon and glass fiber fabrics as nanoscale reinforcement material, and the effects of their conductivity, degree of reinforcement and stacking sequences on the overall multiscale composite properties are investigated.

2 Theoretical

There are usually three mechanisms involved in EMI shielding. As shown in Fig. 1, *reflection* (R) is usually the first mechanism of EMI shielding. For reflection of the radiation by the shield, the shield must have mobile charge carriers (electrons or holes) that interact with the electromagnetic field in the radiation [2]. A quantum view of EMF explains this interaction. SE by *absorption* is the second mechanism which requires the shield to have electric and/or magnetic dipoles which could vibrate through interaction with the electromagnetic field, resulting in phonon generation (heat in material). The higher the reflection capacity of a material, the smaller the absorption mechanism is involved. *Multiple-reflection* (MR) which represents the internal reflections within the shielding material is usually the third mechanism. It is a positive or negative term which needs to be taken into account when the absorption loss is less than 15 dB [7]. A theoretical model of SE of multilayered structure in the far field radiation regime (plane wave) is given in [7]. The far field regime means that the distance between the radiation source and the shielding material is higher than $\lambda/2\pi$, Where λ is the free-space wavelength of the radiation to be shielded [5, 7]. SE is defined by the ratio of transmitted power (P_t) through the material to the incident power (P_i) [7].

$$SE = -10 \log \left(\frac{P_t}{P_i} \right) = -20 \log \left(\frac{|E_t|}{|E_i|} \right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1 Incident waves from air impinging a material. The attenuation is shown as well as differences between reflection and multiple-reflection mechanisms

3 Experimental

3.1 Materials

The MWCNTs with purity of > 95% and diameter range of 10-15 nm were purchased from Hanwha Nanotech. Plain-woven 3K carbon fibers and DBLT glass fibers were supplied by JMC (Gyeongju, Korea) and Jet Korea (Changwon, Korea), respectively. Unsaturated polyester resin, curing agent, and catalyst were supplied by Cray Valley Korea, Arkema, and Jet Korea, respectively.

3.2 Fabrication

First, MWCNTs were horn-sonicated in methanol at a concentration of 1g/L for 30 min to obtain a MWCNT suspension. Fiber textile preforms were then coated with MWCNTs by the spraying the MWCNT suspension using a spray gun. Methanol was then removed by drying the MWCNT-coated preforms in a vacuum oven at 60°C. Multiscale hybrid composites were then manufactured via vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). Vacuum was used to pull the neat resin into the preform (woven carbon and glass fiber), and the

resin was subsequently allowed to cure. Illustration of the difference between the common configuration where the resin is first mixed with the filler and the aforementioned configuration is shown in Fig. 2. In case (a), the CNMs are dispersed throughout the fiber-resin system, while in case (b), the CNMs are physically adhered to the fiber surface via van der Waals interaction. In essence, in case (b), MWCNT form a densely packed thin layer on the fiber textile. In this study, case (b) was employed.

Fig. 2 Two material configurations to be used: (a) CNMs are dispersed in resin, (b) CNMs are sprayed on the preform

Case (a) poses a disadvantage of limited CNM content that can be achieved due to the increasing resin viscosity with increasing CNM loading. Up to 0.2 wt.% of CNM with respect to resin has been achieved. On the contrary, case (b) has the advantage of much higher CNM content with controlled network structure. However, the drawback of case (b) may be the capability of achieving a great filler thickness. For instance, we sprayed for each deposited layer a quantity of 0.1 g over a 200 X 200 mm² woven fiber surface, and this corresponds to a thickness of ~0.188 micrometer assuming no porosity.

Curing of unsaturated polyester resin was done in ambient air, and the EMI SE was measured using type N connectors with a test system in accord with ASTM-D4935 at Nano Convergence Practical Application Center (Daegu, Korea).

Ten composites were tested, and their constructions are schematically illustrated in Fig. 3.

The samples in case (a) are essentially based on carbon fibers where the position as well as the thickness of the sprayed CNT layer is varied to investigate the effect on EMI SE. The same configurations were employed in the case of glass fibers, as illustrated in case (b). In case (c) the constructions were designed such that the stacking

sequence of glass (dielectric) and carbon (conductive) fibers was varied.

Fig. 3 Composite layers arrangement. Case (a) is associated with carbon fibers, case (b) with glass fibers. Case (c) include alternating and sandwich structures (between carbon and glass fiber layers).

4 Results and Discussions

Prior to CNT spraying onto fiber performs, CNTs were first sprayed onto a PET film to characterize electrical properties of the filler film with its thickness. SEM images were taken on the sprayed sample, and Fig. 4 shows the case of a twice-sprayed layer (0.1 g of CNT over a 200 X 200 mm² area per spray), which is characterized by a dense network of entangled CNTs. Volume conductivities measured

after each coating showed 1.18S/cm and 1.15S/cm, respectively. Surface resistivities were measured to be 82.4 and 43.88 Ω/sq, respectively.

Fig. 4 SEM image of CNT-sprayed-coated PET film

Carbon fiber and MWNT can be classified as good conductors, which reduces their attenuation constant according to the following expression [7]:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\pi \mu f \sigma} \left(\frac{Np}{m} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where α is the attenuation constant, μ is the magnetic permeability, and m is the length unit (meter). The attenuation constant is related to the skin depth δ (depth at which the electromagnetic field decreases to 1/e of the incident value in a good conductor) by the following [7]:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

The skin depth is thus inversely proportional to the frequency, since conductivity and magnetic permeability are constant values (since we are not dealing with ferromagnetic materials), which means that for good conductors, the higher the frequency, the higher the attenuation constant, but the overall EMI SE levels off to a certain level with respect to the nature of the material. This phenomenon can be view on Figs. 5 and 6 by 220 and 420 MHz, respectively.

Fig. 5 Attenuation in decibels in the case of carbon fiber based multiscale composites.

Fig. 6 Attenuation in decibels in the case of sandwich fibers based multiscale composites.

In Fig. 5 (carbon fiber based composites), we investigated the effect of spraying CNT layers on

fibers. For all the four cases, no great changes was observed especially in high frequency regimes, that is, from around 200 MHz to 1500 MHz. This can be attributed to the high conductivity of carbon fiber; thus, the effect of relatively thin CNT layers did not significantly influence the EMI SE of the base materials. In fact, it is known that the dominant shielding mechanism for highly conductive materials is a combination of reflection and multiple reflection (if the absorption mechanism ranges allow). The penetration loss of a wave passing through a shield material of thickness l is given by [7] :

$$A = \alpha l \text{ nepers} = 8.686\alpha l \text{ dB} \quad (5)$$

For a double sprayed layer, the absorption loss is in the order of 0.044 dB, which is quite small, which suggests that multiple reflection cannot be neglected. It can contribute either positively or negatively, and this is why the sprayed MWCNTs did not significantly influence the EMI SE of carbon fiber based composites.

On the other hand in Fig. 7 where the samples are essentially based on dielectric materials (glass fibers and unsaturated polyester), it is evident that the presence of CNTs significantly increases the EMI SE, since it manifests a new mode of contribution that was not encountered before in case of glass fiber composites. And it is shown that the more the CNT layers are concentrated in the center of the composite, the greater the EMI SE, which may be due to the fact that the negative effect of multiple reflection is neutralized as the overall thickness is now surrounded by glass fibers. However, the overall SE was low (< 10 dB) for practical applications, as compared to carbon fiber based composites (in the order of 80 dB). Therefore, efforts need to be made to utilize CMNs to dramatically enhance the SE of glass fiber based composites.

Figure 6, on the other hand, shows an interesting phenomenon, where the alternating and sandwich constructions showed crossing SE's at a certain frequency. We obtained a shielding level in the same range as in the case of only neat carbon fibers, this is 80.5 dB at 142 MHz, when we alternated glass and carbon fibers. However, from 439 MHz to 1.5 GHz, the sandwich structures showed EMI SE higher than the case of alternating carbon and glass fibers which .

Fig. 7 Attenuation in decibels in the case of glass fiber based multiscale composites.

instead decreased creating a crossing point as shown on figure 6. This shows that SE is sensitive to fiber stacking sequence as well as the frequency, and warrants further investigation.

4 Conclusions.

In this work, we investigated the EMI SE of multiscale composites using MWNT as nano-reinforcement. A SE level of greater than 80 dB was obtained for carbon fiber based composites as well as composites with alternating and sandwich structures. The effect of MWNT was not significant in the case of carbon fiber based composites; while it improved EMI SE in the case glass fiber based composites. It is clear that further work need to be done to improved the SE of glass fiber composites.

References

- [1] M. Kato "Electromagnetics in biology" 1st edition, Springer, 2006.
- [2] Junhua Wu, D.D.L. Chung "Increasing the electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness of carbon fiber polymer -matrix composite by using

activated carbon fibers". *Carbon*, Vol. 40, pp 445-467, 2002.

- [3] Christopher J. Von Klemperer, Denver Maharaj "Composites electromagnetic interference shielding materials for aerospace applications". *Composite structure*, Vol. 91, pp 467-472, 2009.
- [4] Wern Shiarng Jou "The high electromagnetic shielding of wove carbon fiber composites applied to optoelectronic devices". *IEE transactions on electromagnetic compatibility*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp 755
- [5] Mohammed H. Al-Saleh, Uttandaraman Sundararaj "Electromagnetic interference shielding mechanism of CNT/polymer composites". *Carbon*, Vol. 47, pp 1738-1746, 2009.
- [6] J. G. Park, J. Louis, Q. Cheng, J. Bao, J. Smithyman, R. Liang, B. Wang, C. Zhang, J. S. Brooks, L. Kramer, P. Fanchasis, D. Dorrough "electromagnetic interference shielding properties of carbon nanotube buckypaper composites". *Nanotechnology*, Vol. 20, pp 415702-9.
- [7] R. B. Schulz, V.C. Plantz, D. R. Brush "Shielding theory and practice". *IEE transactions on electromagnetic compatibility*, Vol. 30, No. 3, pp 187-201, 1988.